

Congruence speed of tetration bases ending with 0

Marco Ripà

Rome, Italy

e-mail: marcokrt1984@yahoo.it

Abstract: For every non-negative integer a and positive integer b , the congruence speed of the tetration ${}^b a$ is the difference between the number of the rightmost digits of ${}^b a$ that are the same as those of ${}^{b+1} a$ and the number of the rightmost digits of ${}^{b-1} a$ that are the same as those of ${}^b a$. In the decimal numeral system, if the given base a is not a multiple of 10, as $b := b(a)$ becomes sufficiently large, we know that the value of the congruence speed does not depend on b anymore, otherwise the number of the new rightmost zeros of ${}^b a$ drastically increases for any unit increment of b and, for this reason, we have not previously described the congruence speed of a when it is a multiple of 10. This short note fills the gap by giving the formula for the congruence speed of the mentioned values of a at any given height of the hyperexponent.

Keywords: Tetration, Exponentiation, Congruence speed, Modular arithmetic, Recurring digits.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification: Primary 11A07; Secondary 11D79.

1 Introduction

For any given pair of non-negative integers (a, b) , we call *tetration* the 4th degree hyperoperator which is recursively defined as

$${}^b a = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } b = 0 \\ a^{({}^{b-1} a)} & \text{if } b \geq 1 \end{cases}.$$

For this purpose, it is interesting to note that we can also extend the above to a negative value of the hyperexponent since, assuming $\bar{b} \in \mathbb{N}_0 \cup \{-1\}$, $\bar{b} a = \log_a ({}^{\bar{b}+1} a)$ allows us to state ${}^{-1} a = \log_a (a^0) = \log_a (1) = 0$ and even go beyond (see References [1] and [2], Section 3).

Assuming radix-10 (i.e., the decimal numeral system), for every a that is not a multiple of 10, it is well known [4] that tetration has a peculiar property, named by the author as “constancy of the congruence speed”, which we can translate as the fact that, for every sufficiently large $b := b(a)$ (for a tight bound, consider the sufficient condition $\tilde{v}(a) + 2$, where

$$\tilde{v}(a) := \begin{cases} v_5(a-1) & \text{iff } a \equiv 1 \pmod{5} \\ v_5(a^2+1) & \text{iff } a \equiv \{2, 3\} \pmod{5} \\ v_5(a+1) & \text{iff } a \equiv 4 \pmod{5} \\ v_2(a^2-1) - 1 & \text{iff } a \equiv 5 \pmod{10} \end{cases},$$

while $v_2(m)$ and $v_5(m)$ indicates the 2-adic and the 5-adic valuation of m , respectively), the number of the rightmost digits of ${}^b a$ that are the same as those of ${}^{b+1} a$ minus the number of the rightmost digits of ${}^{b-1} a$ that remain the same by moving to ${}^b a$ is equal to the number of the new rightmost digits that freeze when we move from ${}^{b+k} a$ to ${}^{b+k+1} a$, for every $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ (see Definitions 1.1 to 1.3 of Reference [5]).

Now, for each non-negative integer a , let us indicate the number of new frozen digits at height $b \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ as $V(a, b)$, while $V(a)$ denotes the (fixed) value of the constant congruence speed of a (i.e., the non-negative integer returned by $V(a, b)$ for any $b \geq \tilde{v}(a) + 2$).

As an example, let us take $a = 807$. Then, we have $V(807, 1) = 0$, $V(807, 2) = 4$, $V(807, 3) = 4$, $V(807, 4) = 4$, $V(807, 5) = 4$, and finally $V(807, 6) = V(807, 7) = \dots = V(807) = 3$ since $\tilde{v}_5(807^2 + 1) + 2 = 4 + 2 = 6$ (by Definition 2.1 of Reference [5]) and

$${}^1 807 = 807;$$

$${}^2 807 \equiv 54962039628331827388850173\mathbf{7943} \pmod{10^{30}};$$

$${}^3 807 \equiv 6016926514668229405256\mathbf{32857943} \pmod{10^{30}};$$

$${}^4 807 \equiv 146336906474874632\mathbf{626032857943} \pmod{10^{30}};$$

$${}^5 807 \equiv 35503490744897\mathbf{3150626032857943} \pmod{10^{30}};$$

$${}^6 807 \equiv 47863568981\mathbf{2283150626032857943} \pmod{10^{30}};$$

$${}^7 807 \equiv 02704888\mathbf{8762283150626032857943} \pmod{10^{30}};$$

\vdots

$$({}^{1\text{googolplex}}) 807 \equiv \mathbf{803001638762283150626032857943} \pmod{10^{30}}.$$

References [3–5] describe the value of $V(a, b)$ for any a that is not multiple of 10. In particular, Equation (16) of Reference [5] gives the exact value of $V(a)$ for all the mentioned tetration bases.

Accordingly, in Section 2, we provide the formula for every $V(a, b)$ such that a is congruent to 0 modulo 10 (we point out that if a is a multiple of 10, then there does not exist any b which stabilizes the congruence speed of the base and thus $V(a)$ is always undefined).

2 Congruence speed of all the tetration bases congruent to 0 modulo 10

Let $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$ not be a multiple of 10, while $b, c \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, and assume radix-10 (as usual). Then, the congruence speed of the tetration ${}^b a := j \cdot 10^c$ (i.e., the last digit of a is equal to 0), is given by the difference between the number of the rightmost (trailing) 0's at height b and the number of the rightmost 0's at height $b - 1$.

Given the fact that $j \not\equiv 0 \pmod{10}$ trivially implies $j^{(b-1)(j \cdot 10^c)} \not\equiv 0 \pmod{10}$, the number of the rightmost 0's of ${}^b(j \cdot 10^c)$ is the same as the ending 0's of $10^{c \cdot (b-1)(j \cdot 10^c)}$ since ${}^b(j \cdot 10^c) = j^{(b-1)(j \cdot 10^c)} \cdot 10^{(c \cdot (b-1)(j \cdot 10^c))}$.

Thus, the tetration ${}^b(j \cdot 10^c)$ is always congruent to 0 modulo $10^{(c \cdot (b-1)(j \cdot 10^c))}$, whereas ${}^b(j \cdot 10^c) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{10^{(1+c \cdot (b-1)(j \cdot 10^c))}}$, and it follows that ${}^b(j \cdot 10^c)$ has a total of (exactly) $c \cdot (b-1)(j \cdot 10^c)$ trailing zeros on the right side.

Hence, as long as j , $b - 1$, and c are positive integers,

$$V(j \cdot 10^c, b) = c \cdot ({}^{b-1}(j \cdot 10^c)) - c \cdot ({}^{b-2}(j \cdot 10^c)) = c \cdot ({}^{b-1}(j \cdot 10^c) - {}^{b-2}(j \cdot 10^c)) \quad (1)$$

(e.g., if $a = 300 = 3 \cdot 10^2$ and $b = 3$, then $V(3 \cdot 10^2, 3) = 2 \cdot (300^{300} - 300) = 2 \cdot 3^{300} - 600$).

Now, we observe that $0^0 = 1$ implies that ${}^b 0 = 1$ if and only if b is even, whereas ${}^b 0 = 0$ for any odd value of b .

Consequently, $V(0, b) = 0$ for every positive integer b .

Therefore, we can conclude that

$$a := j \cdot 10^c \Rightarrow V(a, b) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{iff } j = 0 \\ c & \text{iff } j \neq 0 \wedge b = 1 \\ c \cdot ({}^{b-1}(j \cdot 10^c) - {}^{b-2}(j \cdot 10^c)) & \forall j, b - 1, c \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

holds as long as $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$ is not a multiple of 10, while b and c are two (strictly) positive integers.

3 Conclusion

Since we can recursively extend integer tetration so that ${}^{-1}a$ is well-defined (see Section 1), Equation (2), which gives the value of $V(a, b)$ for all the tetration bases that have 0 as their rightmost digit, can be compactly rewritten (for all $b \in \mathbb{Z}^+$) as

$$V(j \cdot 10^c, b) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{iff } j = 0 \\ c \cdot ({}^{b-1}(j \cdot 10^c) - {}^{b-2}(j \cdot 10^c)) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

and this concludes the present note, together with the description of the congruence speed of the tetration bases that we did not include in our previous papers.

References

- [1] D. Kouznetsov. Solution of $F(z + 1) = \exp(F(z))$ in complex z -plane. *Math. Comp.*, **78**(267):1647–1670, 2009.
- [2] W. Paulsen. Tetration for complex bases. *Adv. Comput. Math.*, **45**(6):243–267, 2019.
- [3] M. Ripà. On the constant congruence speed of tetration. *Notes Number Theory Discret. Math.*, **26**(3):245–260, 2020.
- [4] M. Ripà. The congruence speed formula. *Notes Number Theory Discret. Math.*, **27**(4):43–61, 2021.
- [5] M. Ripà and L. Onnis. Number of stable digits of any integer tetration. *Notes Number Theory Discret. Math.*, **28**(3):441–457, 2022.